

Original Article

Estimation of Dusenberry-Eckstein Consumption Model in Comparison with Davis-SK model: An Empirical Analysis of South Punjab

Muhammad Aurmaghan¹, Muhammad Zahir Faridi², Khawaja Asif Mehmood³, & Sidra Ilyas⁴

¹ PhD Scholar, School of Economics, Bahauddin Zakariya University, Multan, Punjab, Pakistan.

² Professor of Economics, School of Economics, Bahauddin Zakariya University, Multan, Punjab, Pakistan.

³ Assistant Professor, School of Economics, Bahauddin Zakariya University, Multan, Punjab, Pakistan.

⁴ Assistant Professor, School of Economics, Bahauddin Zakariya University, Multan, Punjab, Pakistan.

Abstract

The focus of this study, which is part of the broader research effort in South Punjab, Pakistan, centers around the application of consumption hypotheses such as the Relative Income Hypothesis (RIH) along with its Duesenberry, Eckstein, and Fromm (DEF) and Davis-SK adaptations. The study employs cross-sectional data sampled over 802 households from South Punjab during the 2022–23 year. In particular, the study attempts to validate the demonstration and ratchet effects proposed by Dusenberry using Ordinary Least Squares (OLS) regression. The sociological and economic factors integrated into the study include household income, education, family size, marital status, locality, and gender, enabling the analysis of their impact on household consumption. The region's relative income hypothesis is validated and significantly determines the presence of both the demonstration and ratchet effects. The results reveal the need to include post-psychological and social attributes of consumption behavior in economic frameworks, particularly with developing countries reflecting extreme income inequality gaps. This literature gaps along with the literature on consumption is peculiarly the purpose of this study, which was made possible with the new insights provided through disaggregated household-level datasets, outlining the need for policy frameworks considering socio-economic welfare enhancement and poverty alleviation indicators for South Punjab.

Keywords: Keynesian Consumption, Relative Income Hypothesis, Cross-Sectional Data, South Punjab-Pakistan

Introduction

In any economy, household consumption is one of the most important determinants of aggregate demand and economic activity. In developing economies like Pakistan, poverty and inequality are pressing concerns; therefore, an understanding of the factors that influence consumption is important. South Punjab is one of region in Pakistan that has to deal with so many socio-economic problems, directly influencing consumer attitudes. Consumer behavior is analyzed through economic theories such as the Keynesian Absolute Consumption hypothesis, Life-Cycle Hypotheses, and the Permanent Income Hypothesis (Friedman, 1957; Modigliani & Brumberg, 1954). These frameworks, while considering current income, expected future income, and wealth accumulation, offer fascinating perspectives on the decision-making process of an individual consumer. Research on consumer behavior in South Punjab, where agriculture is a key sector, often integrates with agricultural economics and rural development (Ali & Ahmad, 2020). As far, Pakistan is concerned, estimating the consumption hypothesis is not new. Most of the literature has used aggregated main data, but a few studies are found that focus on cross-sectional analysis for South Punjab, Pakistan.

The major contribution of current study is the utilization of cross-sectional data from the household sector in the southern region of Punjab, Pakistan and of examining various notions of the relative income hypothesis of

JOURNAL OF
SOCIAL HORIZONS

Copyright © The Author(s). 2025

This is an open-access article distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribute 4.0 International License, which permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided the original author(s) and source are credited.

How to Cite:

Aurmaghan, M., Faridi, M. Z., Mehmood, K. A., & Ilyas, S. (2025). Estimation of Dusenberry-Eckstein Consumption Model in Comparison with Davis-SK model: An Empirical Analysis of South Punjab. *Journal of Social Horizons*, 2(2), 1-10.
[https:// 10.5281/zenodo.15663247](https://10.5281/zenodo.15663247)

* Corresponding Author: Muhammad Zahir Faridi | Professor of Economics, School of Economics, Bahauddin Zakariya University, Multan, Punjab, Pakistan.

✉ zahirfaridi@bzu.edu.pk

© 2025 | College of Education, Swabi, Pakistan.

consumption. Though investigation of local consumption patterns is thus necessary to fully grasp these particular traits. Skoufias and Quisumbing (2005) argued that the volatility and uncertainty of income greatly affect consumers' purchasing choices in an agricultural economy. The consumption pattern at the household level can also be influenced by government policies, which include setting up social safety nets and subsidizing basic commodities (Haider et al., 2019). This initiative must be evaluated in its effectiveness and efficiency towards improving humanitarian outcomes and decreasing poverty levels in South Punjab; this has been a blistering topic of discussion in research but ironically does not feature prominently in the consumer behaviour studies of this region in South Punjab. The present study fills up to the gap by exploring the determinants of regional level household consumption decision based on the cross-sectional study.

Dusenberry's relative income hypothesis proposes that the consumption function curve shifts upward to maintain a constant average propensity to consume. The consumers grow acclimated to their greater level of spending and find it very hard to decrease their spending when their income decreases (Keynes, 1936). In the view of Dusenberry (1954), a person's consumption is not determined by their current income but by a specific level of income they have achieved in the past. What matters more than an individual's absolute income, in his view, is how that income compares to others in society; in other words, how much a person spends is how he or she perceives about the income distribution.

Empirical research conducted by Kuznets (1962) for the period 1869 to 1938, based on time-series data. It indicates that the average tendency to consume is relatively stable over an extended period. (Kuznet, 1962). The households keep spending the same amount as earlier by cutting back their savings. Consequently, contrary to what one might expect from family budget studies, people's consumer expenditure does not reduce significantly when their income falls as it does during recessions or depressions.

The objective of the study is to evaluate modified relative income hypothesis models which includes DEF and Davis-SK specifications for consumption.

Literature Review

The current study is primarily based on analyzing Relative Income Hypothesis of Duesenberry developed in 1949 which suggests that both absolute and relative income levels do impact consumption behavior.

DEF (1960) simulated systemic behaviour of the U.S. economy in the face of recession to highlight the importance of relative income in economic behaviour. This study provides a fine-grained examination of consumers' behaviour with a multi-faceted perception and their reactions to economic contractions, questioning the extent to which the consumption and economic decisions of people are affected by their relative income rank positions. The simulation suggests that the reduction in actual expenditure during a recession is achieved not by an absolute reduction in income but through the relative perception of that income in comparison to income of those in the social cohort. Social comparison theory provides the theoretical basis for this phenomenon, which individuals compare the welfare of others against themselves. Classical economic models, where only changes in absolute income are considered, may ignore these important factors, and we may stay away from such analyses with inadequate knowledge of how consumers behave under economic changes. The model of DEF (1960) presents a useful framework for understanding how economic conditions, social comparisons, and consumer behavior are interdependent, and more complete account of the dynamic of the economy during business contractions.

Ando and Modigliani (1963) clarified the consumption hypothesis utilizing both cross-sectional and time series data. The utility functions were the first thing that the model accounted for since it was presumed that utility was a function of the overall amount of money spent. It was presumed that the utility must be homogeneous and that the individual would not choose to abandon his/her inheritance or receive it if it was given to him/her. The consumer always plan to spend money regardless of age. The final hypothesis stated that the average income during the earning period would be the same no matter what age group was being considered. It has been demonstrated that the consumption function is capable of accounting not only for the long-run stability but also for the cyclical fluctuation of the ratios of saving and income.

Lindley and Lorgelly (2005) examined the relative income hypothesis, which seeks to ascertain the impact of economic inequality on health outcomes. The research utilized data from the British Household Panel Survey spanning the years 1991 to 2001. The results of the study indicate that the notion of relative income cannot be

substantiated within the historical framework of Britain. The research emphasizes the importance of scientists prioritizing the reduction of contamination and the enhancement of resistance in the inequality index.

Ball and Chernova (2008) investigated the effect of absolute and relative income levels on a person's degree of happiness. The study's findings indicate that happiness is correlated favorably with both absolute and relative levels of money. It has also been demonstrated that a change in relative income has a greater impact on a person's level of happiness than does a change in absolute income. When compared to the influence of non-financial elements on one's level of happiness, such as personal relationships, employment, jobs, and health, the effect of measured absolute household income is rather insignificant.

Khalid and Khan (2011) examined the homogeneity of household purchasing patterns across the country's four provinces. They also examined differences in urban regions within each province using micro-level household data from 2001 to 2008. The results indicated that food and beverages were the biggest proportion of overall household consumption expenditures across all provinces, with households of higher socioeconomic status allocating a much greater amount of their budget to this category. As per the data, households in all provinces account for the largest amount of overall consumption and expenditures. Moreover, urban households allocate a somewhat higher proportion of their spending towards housing in comparison to rural households.

Ajmair and Akhtar (2012) examined the variables influencing household consumption. The parameters under consideration include income, family size, and fundamental necessities. Findings confirm that there exists a considerable propensity for spending within high-income categories since households affiliated with higher-income groups exhibit elevated levels of consumption. The findings of the study indicate that there exists a positive relationship between all variables and consumption, except age. The study additionally illustrates a negative correlation between age and consumption, indicating that as individuals become older, their levels of consumption tend to decline. Furthermore, findings indicate that education exerts a beneficial impact on consumption patterns. Educated households tend to exhibit elevated levels of consumption due to their commitment to upholding a particular quality of living.

Khan (2014) investigated the relationship between farm household consumption and income in the Peshawar, Khyber Pakhtunkhwa, Pakistan, area. The data was primarily obtained within the specified time frame in 2012. The findings indicate that three independent variables, namely household education, household income, and family size, exhibited a positive and highly significant regression coefficient. Conversely, age demonstrated a negative coefficient.

Iancu and Sandica (2014) conducted a study that specifically investigated the applicability of the random walk hypothesis in the Romanian economy, within the framework of permanent income theory. They found that to comprehend the makeup of consuming behavior within a larger societal framework, it is essential to include components of the random walk consumption model. It also looks at the wild swings in the patterns of global spending.

Islam et al. (2018) conducted a study to examine the relationship between the relative income hypothesis and household energy consumption decisions in emerging regions. The analysis incorporated the Verma model, which integrated statistical and economic methodologies. The sample size of the study consisted of 5,140 households. The results demonstrate that all variables exhibited statistical significance across all established models. Therefore, the findings of the study indicate that policies and programs should prioritize the improvement of individual income levels. Strategies such as generational employment, wealth creation, government expenditure rise, small and medium-scale industry empowerment, and skill development can enhance income levels.

Adhikari (2022) investigated the prevalence of Duesenberry's relative income theory within the context of the Nepalese economy. Time series data spanning the years 1974 through 2020 were used in the study. The economy of Nepal exhibits a high proportion of consumption, resulting in a correspondingly low rate of saving. Insufficient growth in capital formation in Nepal was a consequence of the absence of savings. The results indicate that there is a requirement to enhance the rate of capital formation to stimulate higher levels of income and employment within the Nepalese economy.

The Relative Income Hypothesis of Duesenberry and empirically examined by Lindley and Lorgelly (2005), emphasize the role played by social and psychological factors in consumption patterns. This hypothesis argues that people's consumption is not only determined by the level of their absolute income but also by their relative position with respect to the income of others. Ball and Chernova (2008) and Khan and Khalid (2011) have undertaken

studies that illustrate how the relative income and social comparisons influences consumer satisfaction and consumer spending.

The knowledge of consumer behavior is essential for firms if they are to develop marketing strategies, product designs, and pricing policies that have compatibility with consumer preferences and also can generate a maximum profit (Lancaster (1966). Consumption decisions have an impact on household finances and well-being. Understanding how people divide their income between consumption and saving provides insight into their financial security, debt management, and long-term planning, such as retirement savings and education funding Modigliani & Brumberg, (1963; 1980). Individual consumer behavior is influenced by factors such as income inequality, social norms, and access to credit, which in turn affect a person's overall society well-being and economic inequality (Duesenberry, 1949).

Theoretical Framework

Duesenberry (1949) stated that individuals' consumption behaviors are irreversible, which indicates that as income rises, individuals' consumption rises dramatically; yet, as income falls, consumption remains stable rather than falling. We refer to this tendency as the "Ratchet Effect." According to the relative income hypothesis, an individual's consumption is influenced by their relative income position rather than only their absolute income, as per Keynes's theory. As discussed in the previous section, we have discussed the Keynesian Absolute Income-Consumption hypothesis that the consumption expenditure of a family depends only on absolute income. Now, we discuss the relative income hypothesis which emphasizes that family consumption expenditure depends on the relative consumption and income of the other people (Applanaidu & Islam, 2018). Households' consumption expenditures are influenced by other households' consumption patterns. The people make efforts to maintain the pattern of their consumption according to the average consumption pattern of other people in society (Kosicki, 1987). Moreover, the consumption of the household in society is determined by the expenditure of the community residing in the surrounding's. The consumption of a household is influenced by the highest level of income that is previously attained by the household (Khan, 2014; Bisset & Tenaw, 2020; Mason, 2000).

The theoretical framework of Dusenberry's hypothesis of relative income was developed by Singh and Kumar (1971). The bases of the relative income hypothesis lie in the socio-psychological consumer behavior. It is based on the two axioms.

- i) The household behavior of consumption is not independent but interdependent which is called the demonstration effect¹.
- ii) The consumption behavior of the household is not reversible over time. It is called the ratchet effect².

The functional form of Dusenberry's consumption hypothesis is given by the following equation

$$\left(\frac{C}{Y}\right)_i = \beta_0 + \beta_1 \left(\frac{Y}{Y_0}\right)_i \quad (A)$$

Where C = Household consumption expenditure.

Y = household disposable personal income.

Y_0 = Peak or highest income of the household

β_0 and β_1 are parameters. In general, the value of β_1 is negative. The consumption income ratio is higher when 'Y' is less than ' Y_0 '.

To examine Dusenberry hypothesis of relative income we have original Dusenberry model

$$\left(\frac{C}{Y}\right)_i = \alpha^o + \beta_1 \left(\frac{Y}{Y^o}\right)_i + \mu i$$

¹ For an individual's consumption decisions, relative income is more important than absolute income.

² The consumption habits formed by an individual in the past have a substantial influence on their current consumption.

Dusenbery, Eckstein and Fromm (1960) have designed a consumption function with some modifications in Dusenbery's (1949) original consumption hypothesis in 1960 by replacing the individual consumption-income

ratio $\left(\frac{C}{Y}\right)_i$, with desired or expected consumption-income ratio

$$\left(\frac{C}{Y}\right)_i^* = \beta_0 + \beta_1 \left(\frac{Y}{Y_0}\right)_i \quad (B)$$

The desired consumption-income ratio may be determined by Nerlove (1956)³ through a partial adjustment process. This is given as follows,

$$\left[\left(\frac{C}{Y}\right)_i - \left(\frac{C}{Y}\right)_{i-1}\right] = \lambda \left[\left(\frac{C}{Y}\right)_i^* - \left(\frac{C}{Y}\right)_{i-1}\right]$$

$$\left[\left(\frac{C}{Y}\right)_i - \left(\frac{C}{Y}\right)_{i-1}\right] = \lambda \left(\frac{C}{Y}\right)_i^* - \lambda \left(\frac{C}{Y}\right)_{i-1}$$

Adding both sides $\left(\frac{C}{Y}\right)_{i-1}$

$$\left(\frac{C}{Y}\right)_i - \cancel{\left(\frac{C}{Y}\right)_{i-1}} + \cancel{\left(\frac{C}{Y}\right)_{i-1}} = \lambda \left(\frac{C}{Y}\right)_i^* - \lambda \left(\frac{C}{Y}\right)_{i-1} + \left(\frac{C}{Y}\right)_{i-1}$$

By putting the value of $\left(\frac{C}{Y}\right)_i^*$ in equation

$$\left(\frac{C}{Y}\right)_i = \lambda \left[\beta_0 + \beta_1 \left(\frac{Y}{Y_0}\right)_i\right] + (1-\lambda) \left(\frac{C}{Y}\right)_{i-1}$$

$$\left(\frac{C}{Y}\right)_i = \lambda \beta_0 + \lambda \beta_1 \left(\frac{Y}{Y_0}\right)_i + (1-\lambda) \left(\frac{C}{Y}\right)_{i-1}$$

let $\alpha_0 = \lambda \beta_0, \alpha_1 = \lambda \beta_1, a_2 = (1-\lambda)$

$$\left(\frac{C}{Y}\right)_i = \alpha_0 + \alpha_1 \left(\frac{Y}{Y_0}\right)_i + a_2 \left(\frac{C}{Y}\right)_{i-1} \quad (C)$$

Equation (C) is named as Dusenbery, Eckstein and Fromm (DEF) model or an extended form of the relative income hypothesis model. The parameter α_1 represents Dusenbery's demonstration effect and α_2 indicate the ratchet effect.

To describe the standard of living in a better way, Davis (1952) proposed a new specification of the Relative consumption hypothesis by replacing peak household consumption with the highest or peak household income

$$\left(\frac{C}{Y}\right)_i = \alpha_0 + \alpha_1 \left(\frac{Y}{C_0}\right)_i \quad (D)$$

Equation (D) represents the original Davis model of the relative consumption hypothesis.

Singh and Kumar (1971) specified Davis's equation of relative consumption hypothesis based on the Norlovian partial adjustment process (Nerlove, 1956). SK formulation of relative income hypothesis indicated by the equation (E)

³ The adjustment model was introduced by Nerlove (1956; 1958) by taking into account a single producer with desired output level.

$$\left(\frac{C}{Y}\right)_i = \alpha'_o + \alpha'_1 \left(\frac{Y}{C_o}\right)_i + \lambda' \left(\frac{C}{Y}\right)_{i-1} \quad (E)$$

This model is named as Davis-SK specification of relative income hypothesis. The α'_1 explains the demonstration effect and λ' states the ratchet effect.

Dusenberry-Eckstein and Fromm and Davis-Singh and Kumar specified forms of relative income hypothesis can be empirically used to examine Duesenberry’s demonstration and ratchet-effects by assuming that APC is linearly related to relative income. It shows that the demonstration effect turns out to be the same across households within the various income brackets (Bisset and Tenaw, 2020).

It is argued by McCormick (2018) that households belonging to the high low-income group have less consumption and their APC is low while the people or households belonging to low-income groups have a high value of APC. In developing economies or less developed countries, the value of APC is very high because of the large number of households with low income. That is why, the linear relationship between APC and relative income cannot be an appropriate measure of demonstration effect. Therefore, for an appropriate measure of demonstration effect, it is assumed that APC has a non-linear quadratic form of relationship to relative income. McCormick (2018) has reformulated the Dusenberry-Eckstein and Fromm and Davis-SK specifications by taking the square of the relative income and relative consumption that are given below.

$$\left(\frac{C}{Y}\right)_i = b_o + b_1 \left(\frac{Y}{Y_o}\right)_i + b_2 \left(\frac{Y}{Y_o}\right)_i^2 + \lambda \left(\frac{C}{Y}\right)_{i-1}$$

$$\left(\frac{C}{Y}\right)_i = b'_o + b'_1 \left(\frac{Y}{Y_o}\right)_i + b'_2 \left(\frac{Y}{Y_o}\right)_i^2 + \lambda' \left(\frac{C}{Y}\right)_{i-1}$$

The expected signs of both b_1 and b'_1 are to be negative explaining the strong Dusenberry’s demonstration effect for low-income groups while the expected signs b_2 and b'_2 are to be positive indicating weaker or less powerful Dusenberry’s demonstrations effect for high-income groups.

Measurement of Data and Methodological Issues

Primary data for this study is gathered from the head of household from southern Punjab in Pakistan 2022–2023. Simple random and proportionate selection strategies are the most suitable for this study's data collection from respondents. Data gathering is accomplished through the use of questionnaires.

Table 1

Population and Number of Households of Southern Punjab (Pakistan)

Name of Administrative units	Household	Population
PUNJAB	19,855,902	127,688,922
South Punjab	6296371	40377576

Source: Pakistan Bureau of Statistics (2023)

A total of 802 household heads were interviewed from the southern region of Punjab. The sample size of 802 was obtained using the formula provided below:

$$SS = \frac{z^2 * p(1-p)}{e^2} \div \left(1 + \frac{z^2 * p(1-p)}{e^2 N} \right)$$

Table 1 represents the population and number of households of southern Punjab (Pakistan). The total number of households in Punjab are 19855902 with population over 127688922 no. of persons and households in Southern Punjab are approximately 6,296,371, with population 40377576 persons according to the Pakistan Bureau of Statistics in 2023. A sample size of 802 was determined with a 3.5% margin of error and a 95% confidence interval.

Table 2
Sampling Procedure of Selected Sample

Name of Admin Unit	Total Number of Households	Population	Average Household Size	The number of Respondents
South Punjab	6296371	40377576	6.56	802

Source: Author's calculation based on information obtained from the Pakistan Bureau of Statistics (2023)

Table 2 shows the sampling procedure of selected sample having total number of households are 6296371 with population 40377576, average household size consists of 6.26 persons approx. and number of respondents are 802

Methodology Econometric Methods

The present study has used ordinary least square method for estimation of the model because the analysis is based on the cross-section budget data. The general model is expressed as:

$$Y_i = \beta_0 + \beta_1 X_1 + \beta_2 X_2 + \dots + \beta_k X_k + \mu_i$$

Where Y is dependent variable β_0 is the intercept term and $\beta_1, \beta_2, \beta_3, \dots, \beta_k$, are the slope coefficient of the explanatory variables where μ_i is the error term satisfy all the OLS assumptions.

Model Specification

The present study has specified the following model based on the OLS method.

i) Duesenberry Model

The first model is the original Duesenberry model given below

$$\left(\frac{C}{Y}\right)_i = \beta_0 + \beta_1 \left(\frac{Y}{Y_o}\right)_i + \mu_i$$

Where $\left(\frac{C}{Y}\right)_i$ is average propensity to consume β_0 and β_1 are parameter of the model while $\left(\frac{Y}{Y_o}\right)_i$ is the

demonstration effect and μ_i is the error term

ii) Duesenberry Eckstein-Formm Model

The second model is the modified form of the Dusenberry original model

$$\left(\frac{C}{Y}\right)_i = \alpha + \beta_1 \left(\frac{Y}{Y_o}\right)_i + \gamma' \left(\frac{C}{Y}\right)_{i-1} + \mu_i$$

Where $\left(\frac{C}{Y}\right)_i$ is average propensity to consume β_1 and γ' are parameter of the model $\left(\frac{Y}{Y_o}\right)_i$ is the demonstration

effect, $\left(\frac{C}{Y}\right)_{i-1}$ is the habit ratchet effect and μ_i is the error term

iii) Extended Duesenberry Eckstein Formm with Socio-Economic Variables

We have specified the extended form of DEF model by incorporating socio-economic factors.

$$\left(\frac{C}{Y}\right)_i = \alpha + \beta_1 \left(\frac{Y}{Y_o}\right)_i + \beta_2 \left(\frac{Y}{Y_o}\right)_i^2 + \gamma' \left(\frac{C}{Y}\right)_{i-1} + \beta_3 LOC + \beta_4 STD + \mu_i$$

Where $\left(\frac{C}{Y}\right)_i$ is average propensity to consume $\beta_1, \beta_2, \beta_3, \beta_4$ and γ' are parameter of the model $\left(\frac{Y}{Y_o}\right)_i$ is the

demonstration effect, $\left(\frac{Y}{Y_o}\right)_i^2$ is the income ratchet effect of DEF model, $\left(\frac{C}{Y}\right)_{i-1}$ is the habit ratchet effect, LOC is

the location, STD is the status dummy and μ_i is the error term

And for the Davis model specification is given as

i) Davis – SK Specification

The fourth model of relative income hypothesis is modified by Davis-Singh and Kumar

$$\left(\frac{C}{Y}\right)_i = \alpha + \beta_1 \left(\frac{Y}{C_o}\right)_i + \mu_i$$

Where $\left(\frac{C}{Y}\right)_i$ is average propensity to consume α_o and β_1 are parameter of the model $\left(\frac{Y}{C_o}\right)_i$ is the income consumption ratio or consumption ratchet effect, μ_i is the error term

ii) Davis – SK Specification Extended Model

The fifth model is Davis-Singh and Kumar extended model of relative income.

$$\left(\frac{C}{Y}\right)_i = \alpha + \beta_1 \left(\frac{Y}{C_o}\right)_i + \beta_2 \left(\frac{Y}{C_o}\right)_i^2 + \gamma' \left(\frac{C}{Y}\right)_{i-1} + \mu_i$$

Where $\left(\frac{C}{Y}\right)_i$ is average propensity to consume α_o , β_1 , β_2 and γ' are parameter of the model are parameter of the model $\left(\frac{Y}{C_o}\right)_i$ is the income consumption ratio or consumption ratchet effect, $\left(\frac{Y}{C_o}\right)_i^2$ is the square of Davis S-K consumption ratchet effect, $\left(\frac{C}{Y}\right)_{i-1}$ is the habit ratchet effect and μ_i is the error term.

iii) Extended Davis – SK Specification with Socio-Economic Variables

The sixth model we have extended Davis-Singh and Kumar specification for the relative income hypothesis by adding socio-economic factors.

$$\left(\frac{C}{Y}\right)_i = \alpha + \beta_1 \left(\frac{Y}{C_o}\right)_i + \beta_2 \left(\frac{Y}{C_o}\right)_i^2 + \gamma' \left(\frac{C}{Y}\right)_{i-1} + \beta_3 LOC_i + \beta_4 STD_i + \mu_i$$

Where $\left(\frac{C}{Y}\right)_i$ is average propensity to consume α_o , β_1 , β_3 , β_4 and γ' are parameter of the model $\left(\frac{Y}{C_o}\right)_i$ is the income consumption ratio or consumption ratchet effect, $\left(\frac{Y}{C_o}\right)_i^2$ is the income Davis S-K consumption ratchet effect, $\left(\frac{C}{Y}\right)_{i-1}$ is the habit ratchet effect LOC is the location, STD is the status dummy and μ_i is the error term

Table 3

List of Variables and their Description

Variables	Variables Description	
Dependent Variable		
CON	Total Household Consumption	It provides information on the total amount spent by a household in rupees on food, non-durable goods and services, and durable goods and services.
Explanatory Variables		
INC	Total Household Income	The total income of the household describes the income of the head of the household from all sources in rupees.
$\left(\frac{Y}{Y_o}\right)_i$	Dusenbery Demonstration Effect	Current income divided by past peak income

$\left(\frac{Y}{Y_o}\right)_i^2$	Dusenbery ratchet effect	Income	Square of the household income to past peak income ratio DEF model specification.
$\left(\frac{Y}{C_o}\right)_i$	Consumption Ratchet effect	Ratchet	Current income divided by past peak consumption
$\left(\frac{Y}{C_o}\right)_i^2$	Davis consumption specification	S-K	Square of household income to past peak consumption ratio of Davis S-K model specification.
$\left(\frac{C}{Y}\right)_{i-1}$	Habit Ratchet Effect		past consumption patterns influence current consumption behavior which is lagged consumption income ratio
LOC	Location of residence		It specifies the residential area, whether it be urban or rural if the household resides in an urban region. (1) Otherwise = 0.
STD	Status Dummy		If the household's consumption is influenced by other neighboring household's consumption takes value "1" and it takes the value "0" if the household's consumption of the respondents is not influenced by another household.

Source: Authors own Work

Results and Discussion

This section discusses the findings of Dusenbery's relative income hypothesis by considering the different specified models.

Table 4 explains the findings of original Dusenbery's model with Dusenbery-Eckstein-Fromm Model. The results of extended Dusenbery-Eckstein-Fromm model are discussed in column four. The values of the coefficient of determination are 0.24, 0.308 and 0.31 respectively while the coefficients of adjusted R^2 are 0.23, 0.305, and 0.304 respectively. The coefficients of adjusted R^2 measures the explanatory power of the models. The low values of (R^2) and adjusted R^2 are cross-sectional data phenomena⁴. The F-statistics measures the overall significance level of the model. All three models are overall highly significant at one per cent level of significance. The constant or intercept terms in all three models are positive and highly significant.

Table 4

OLS Estimates of Duesenberry Model and Duesenberry Eckstein Fromm Model for Overall South Punjab

Variables	Duesenberry Original Model	DEF Model	Extended DEF Model
C	0.903 (0.008) [106.811]	0.867 (0.028) [30.756]	0.864 (0.028) [30.551]
$\left(\frac{Y}{Y_o}\right)_i$	-0.647 (0.041) ⁵ [-15.710]	-1.370 (0.106) [-12.910]	-1.399 (0.108) [-12.985]
$\left(\frac{Y}{Y_o}\right)_i^2$	—	0.993 (0.131) [7.611]	1.010 (0.132) [7.660]
$\left(\frac{C}{Y}\right)_{i-1}$	—	0.127 (0.030) [4.287]	0.124 (0.030) [4.192]
Location	—	—	0.011 (0.011)

⁴ Low R^2 values are often obtained in cross-sectional data, probably as a result of the sample's diversity of units.

⁵ The standard errors are shown in round brackets and t-statistics are given in square brackets.

Status dummy	—	—	[0.936] 0.019 (0.014) [1.291]
R-squared	0.236	0.308	0.310
Adjusted R-squared	0.235	0.305	0.306
F-statistic	246.815	118.330	71.622
Prob(F-statistic)	0.000	0.000	0.000
Sample Size	802		

Source: Authors' estimation by using E-Views a statistical software

The intercept term measures the average impact of all omitted categories. We have observed that the coefficient of household income to the highest or peak level of income is not only negative but highly significant at a one per cent level of significance in the original Dusenbery model. The sign of the coefficient confirms the theoretical expected sign. The value of the coefficient is 0.647 with a negative sign. It means that the consumption-to-income ratio or average propensity to consume (APC) falls by about 0.65 units due to a unit increase $\left(\frac{Y}{Y_o}\right)_i$. It indicates

that Dusenbery's demonstration effect is stronger for low-income households. Our findings support Dusenbery's hypothesis and are in line with the findings of Ishtiaq, et al. (2021) and Clark et al. (2009).

In the Dusenberry-Eckstein and Fromm model, the square of household income to highest or peak income ratio is used to combine the issue of low average propensity to consume for high-income households and high average propensity to consume for low-income households (Mc Cormide, 2018; Bisset & Tenaw, 2020).

The coefficient of $\left(\frac{Y}{Y_o}\right)_i^2$ is positive and statistically significant. The findings are theoretically sound and

empirically support Dusenbery's income ratchet effect. The coefficient of $\left(\frac{C}{Y}\right)_{i-1}$ explains the habit ratchet effect

Ishtiaq, et al. (2021). The coefficient of the lagged consumption-to-income ratio is positive and significant at a 5 per cent level of significance. The one-unit increase in $\left(\frac{C}{Y}\right)_{i-1}$, the household consumption increases by about

0.13 units. In the extended DEF model, one has additionally incorporated location and status dummy variables to test the validity of Duesenberry's relative consumption hypothesis for South Punjab in Pakistan.

Both variables have a positive impact on the average propensity to consume. However, both variables are statistically insignificant. The household's consumption is affected by urban area consumption. In addition, the status dummy takes the value of "1" if the household's consumption is influenced by other neighboring household's consumption and it takes the value "0" if otherwise. The value of the coefficient of the status dummy is positive. It means that with an increase of one unit of other neighbor's households' consumption, the household's consumption increases by about 0.019 units. Our findings confirm the results of Duesenberry (1949) Luttmer (2005), Bisset and Tenaw (2020), Mason (2000) and Khan Himayatullah (2014). The Duesenberry-Eckstein and Fromm models have proved that the demonstration and ratchet effect is prevalent in south Punjab.

Table 5 explains the ordinary least square estimates of the original Tom E. Davis model which is the modified form of James Duesendesry model by substituting past peak consumption of a household in lieu of peak income in order to explain the consumption saving behavior of the household regarding demonstration effect. Furthermore, Balvir Singh and Ramesh C. Kumar have extended Davis model retched -effect and habit-retched – effect through

squaring the $\left(\frac{Y}{C_o}\right)_i$ ratio and lagged term $\left(\frac{C}{Y}\right)_{i-1}$.

Table 5 discusses the implications of the relative income consumption hypothesis covering the overall South Punjab cross sectional data. In for column represents OLS estimation of variables in second column results of OLS

estimation are given for Davis model in third and fourth column results of Davis -SK model and Extended Davis -SK model are given respectively.

Table 5

OLS Estimates of Davis-SK Specification for Overall South Punjab

Variables	Davis Model	Davis-SK Model	Extended Davis-SK Model
C	0.903 (0.008) ⁶ [106.811]	0.867 (0.028) [30.75622]	0.864 (0.028) [30.551]
$\left(\frac{Y}{C_o}\right)_i$	-0.402 (0.026) [-15.710]	-0.852 (0.066) [-12.910]	-0.870 (0.067) [-12.985]
$\left(\frac{Y}{C_o}\right)_i^2$	—	0.384 (0.051) [7.611]	0.391 (0.051) [7.660]
$\left(\frac{C}{Y}\right)_{i-1}$	—	0.127 (0.030) [4.287]	0.124 (0.030) [4.192]
Location	—	—	0.011 (0.011) [0.936]
Status dummy	—	—	0.019 (0.014) [1.291]
R-squared	0.236	0.308	0.311
Adjusted R-squared	0.235	0.305	0.306
F-statistic	246.815	118.329	71.622
Prob(F-statistic)	0.000	0.000	0.000
Sample Size		802	

Source: Authors' estimation by using E-Views a statistical software

The values of Co-efficient of Determination (R^2) and Adjusted R^2 for all the models are very low due to cross-sectional data phenomenon⁷. All three models are highly significant overall because the values of F-statistics are 246.81, 118.33, and 71.62 respectively with a one percent level of significance. In the E. Davis model, the value of the constant term is 0.903 while in the Davis-SK model and extended Davis-SK model are almost 0.87 and 0.86 respectively.

We have found that the income to peak consumption ratio $\left(\frac{Y}{C_o}\right)_i$ turns out to be negative and statistically highly significant in the original Davis model and Davis-SK model significations even with extended form. The values of the coefficients are -0.4, -0.85, and -0.87 respectively. This coefficient indicates the demonstration effect based on the Davis-SK significations even with extended form. These negative coefficients mean that the increase in the level of income does not raise the consumption-income ratio significantly. In other words, it means if that is one unit decrease in $\left(\frac{Y}{C_o}\right)_i$ ratio decreases $\left(\frac{C}{Y}\right)_i$ ratio about 0.4 unit in the original' Davis model and almost 0.85 and 0.87 units fall in $\left(\frac{C}{Y}\right)_i$ ratio in Davis-SK model and extended Davis-SK model respectively. It is concluded that there is a prevalence of the Demonstration effect in the overall southern Punjab. In Davis-SK significations the

⁶ Note: The standard errors are shown in round brackets and t-statistics are given in square brackets.

⁷ Low R^2 values are often obtained in cross-sectional data, probably as a result of the sample's diversity of units.

term $\left(\frac{Y}{C_o}\right)_i^2$ shows ratched-effect. We have observed that this term is not only positive in both models but is highly significant at a one percent level of significance. It shows that income consumption ratios $\left(\frac{C}{Y}\right)_i$ do not increase in both models due to a fall in income. During the time of high income, the household attained the highest level of consumption, but when the household's income declines and passes through the recession process, the household consumption will not decrease as much as his income reduces, which means the average propensity to consume decreases. Therefore, the ratched- effect generates a derived relation between income level and APC.

Conclusion

The relative income hypothesis, which emphasizes the influence of community income and consumption patterns on individual household consumption. The results of the study reveal that households' consumption patterns are not only influenced by their absolute income but also by the consumption standards set by their community. This is evident from the significant demonstration and ratchet effects observed, particularly in the DEF and extended DEF models. The study highlights that the consumption-to-income ratio is higher for lower-income households and declines as income rises, indicating stronger demonstration effects among low-income groups.

The regression analysis that we perform regarding South Punjab also provides an elaborate analysis on household consumption behaviour due to relative income effects.

The phenomena of demonstration effect are a general observation in South Punjab, showing that the relative income ranks have significant impacts on consumption. Evidence of ratched-effect and habit-ratched effect is also in abundance, indicating that households continue to consume at a stable level when income increases or decreases.

Our results of the study are aligned with previous research Duesenberry (1949) on relative income and consumption behavior. The demonstration effect, where consumption is influenced by relative income comparisons. Empirical studies by Dynan, Skinner, and Zeldes (2004) provide evidence for the persistence of consumption patterns due to past consumption levels, supporting the ratched-effect and habit-ratched effect observed in this analysis. Furthermore, Luttmer (2005) shows that relative earnings can affect well-being, reinforcing the demonstration effect, while Brown and Taylor (2014) highlight the role of personality traits in financial behavior, which may also interact with consumption patterns in the context of relative income.

As a policy recommendation, it is suggested that the government needs to ensure that the income and consumption patterns of low- and high-income earners is sustained so that the consistency of market functioning is to keep breathing.

References

- Adhikari, R. (2022). Prevalence of Duesenberry's relative income hypothesis in Nepalese economy. *International Review of Business and Economics*, 7(1). <https://doi.org/10.56902/irbe.2022.7.1.2>
- Ajmair, M., & Akhtar, N. (2012). Household Consumption in Pakistan (A case study of district Bhimber, AJK). *European Journal of Scientific Research*, 75(3), 448–457.
- Ali, M., & Ahmad, A. (2020). Agriculture-led Growth Hypothesis: Evidence from Pakistan. *Pakistan Journal of Agricultural Research*, 33(1), 1-11.
- Alimi, R. S. (2013). Keynes' absolute income hypothesis and Kuznets paradox. <https://mpra.ub.uni-muenchen.de/49310/>
- Ando, A., & Modigliani, F. (1963). The "Life Cycle" Hypothesis of Saving: Aggregate Implications and Tests. *American Economic Review*, 53(1), 55-84. <https://www.jstor.org/stable/1817129>
- Ball, R., & Chernova, K. (2008). Absolute income, relative income, and happiness. *Social Indicators Research*, 88(3), 497–529. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11205-007-9217-0>
- Bisset, T., & Tenaw, D. (2020). Keeping up with the Joneses: The relevance of Duesenberry's relative income hypothesis in Ethiopia. In *Research Square*. <https://doi.org/10.21203/rs.3.rs-83692/v1>
- Brown, S., & Taylor, K. (2014). "Household finances and the 'Big Five' personality traits". *Journal of Economic Psychology*, 45, 197-212. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.joep.2014.10.006>
- Clark, A. E., Westergård-Nielsen, N., & Kristensen, N. (2009). Economic satisfaction and income rank in small neighbourhoods. *Journal of the European Economic Association*, 7(2-3), 519-527. <https://doi.org/10.1162/JEEA.2009.7.2-3.519>
- Danlami, A. H., Applanaidu, S.-D., & Islam, R. (2018). Axiom of the relative income hypothesis and household energy choice and consumption in developing areas: Empirical evidence using Verme model. *Kasetsart Journal of Social Sciences*, 39(3), 422–431. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.kjss.2018.06.010>
- Davis, T. E. (1952). The consumption function as a tool for prediction. *The Review of Economics and Statistics*, 34(3), 270. <https://doi.org/10.2307/1925635>
- Duesenberry, J. S. (1948). Income-consumption relations and their implications. *Lloyd Metzler et al., Income, Employment and Public Policy*, New York: WW Norton & Company, Inc.
- Duesenberry, J. S. (1949). *Income, Saving and the Theory of Consumption Behavior*. Harvard University Press.
- Duesenberry, J. S., Eckstein, O., & Fromm, G. (1960). A simulation of the United States economy in recession. *Econometrica: Journal of the Econometric Society*, 28(4), 749. <https://doi.org/10.2307/1907563>
- Dynan, K. E., Skinner, J., & Zeldes, S. P. (2004). Do the rich save more? *Journal of political economy*, 112(2), 397-444.
- Friedman, M. (1957). *A Theory of the Consumption Function*. Princeton University Press.
- Friedman, M. (2018). Theory of the consumption function. In *Theory of the Consumption Function*. Princeton university press.
- Haider, M. A., Raza, M. A., & Malik, H. N. (2019). Impact of Subsidies on Household Consumption Expenditure in Pakistan: Evidence from Household Integrated Economic Survey 2015-16. *The Pakistan Development Review*, 58(4), 541–562.
- Iancu, A. C. A., & Săndică, A.-M. (2014). Testing random walk hypothesis for Romanian consumption: A continuous time approach. *Procedia Economics and Finance*, 15, 228–237. [https://doi.org/10.1016/s2212-5671\(14\)00490-0](https://doi.org/10.1016/s2212-5671(14)00490-0)
- Keynes, J. M. (1936). *The General Theory of Employment, Interest, and Money*. Palgrave Macmillan.
- Khalid, U., & Khan, A. H. (2011). Is Consumption Pattern Homogeneous in Pakistan? Evidence from PSLM 2007-08. *The Pakistan Development Review*, 50(4), 629–648.
- Khan, H. (2014). An empirical investigation of consumption function under relative income hypothesis: Evidence from farm households in northern Pakistan. *International Journal of Economic Sciences*, 3(2), 43-52. https://www.iises.net/download/Soubory/soubory-puvodni/pp43-52iJoES_V3N2.pdf
- Khan, K., & Nishat, M. (2011). Permanent income hypothesis, myopia and liquidity constraints: A case study of Pakistan. *Pakistan Journal of Social Sciences*, 31(2), 299-307. <https://pjss.bzu.edu.pk/index.php/pjss/article/view/116>
- Kosicki, G. (1987). A test of the relative income hypothesis. *Southern Economic Journal*, 54(2), 422. <https://doi.org/10.2307/1059326>
- Kosicki, G. (1987). The relative income hypothesis: A review of the cross section evidence. *Quarterly Journal of Business and Economics*, 26(3), 65–80.

- Kuznets, S. (1962). Quantitative aspects of the economic growth of nations: VII. The share and structures of consumption. *Economic Development and Cultural Change*, 10(2, Part 2), 1–92. <https://doi.org/10.1086/449958>
- Lancaster, K. J. (1966). A new approach to consumer theory. *The Journal of Political Economy*, 74(2), 132–157. <https://doi.org/10.1086/259131>
- Lindley, J., & Lorgelly, P. (2005). The relative income hypothesis: does it exist over time? Evidence from the BHPS.
- Luttmer, E. F. P. (2005). Neighbors as negatives: Relative earnings and well-being. *The Quarterly Journal of Economics*, 120(3), 963–1002. <https://doi.org/10.1162/003355305774268255>
- Mankiw, N. G., & Taylor, M. P. (2014). *Economics*. Cengage Learning.
- Mason, R. (2000). The social significance of consumption: James Duesenberry's contribution to consumer theory. *Journal of Economic Issues*, 34(3), 553–572. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00213624.2000.11506294>
- McCormick, K. (1983). Duesenberry and Veblen: The demonstration effect revisited. *Journal of Economic Issues*, 17(4), 1125–1129. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00213624.1983.11504194>
- McCormick, K. (2018). James Duesenberry as a practitioner of behavioral economics. *Journal of Behavioral Economics for Policy*, 2(1), 13–18.
- Mincer, J., & Polachek, S. (1974). Family investments in human capital: Earnings of women. *The Journal of Political Economy*, 82(2, Part 2), S76–S108. <https://doi.org/10.1086/260293>
- Modigliani, F. (1966). The Life Cycle Hypothesis of Saving, the Demand for Wealth and the Supply of Capital. *Social Research*, 33(2), 160–217.
- Modigliani, F. (1980). The Life Cycle Hypothesis of Saving: Aggregate Implications and Tests. *American Economic Review*, 70(2), 95–124.
- Modigliani, F. (1986). Life cycle, individual thrift, and the wealth of nations. *Science*, 234(4777), 704–712. <https://doi.org/10.1126/science.234.4777.704>
- Modigliani, F., & Brumberg, R. (1954). Utility analysis and the consumption function: An interpretation of cross-section data. *Post-Keynesian Economics*, 1, 338–436.
- Nerlove, M. (1956). Estimates of the elasticities of supply of selected agricultural commodities. *Journal of Farm Economics*, 38(2), 496. <https://doi.org/10.2307/1234389>
- Nerlove, M. (1958). *Distributed lags and demand analysis for agricultural and other commodities* (No. 141). US Government Printing Office.
- Singh, B., & Kumar, R. C. (1971). The relative income hypothesis—a cross country analysis. *The Review of Income and Wealth*, 17(4), 341–348. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1475-4991.1971.tb00787.x>
- Singh, B., Drost, H., & Kumar, R. C. (1978). An empirical evaluation of the relative, the permanent income, and the life-cycle hypotheses. *Economic Development and Cultural Change*, 26(2), 281–305. <https://doi.org/10.1086/451016>
- Skoufias, E., & Quisumbing, A. R. (2005). Consumption insurance and vulnerability to poverty: A synthesis of the evidence from Bangladesh, Ethiopia, Mali, Mexico and Russia. *European Journal of Development Research*, 17(1), 24–58. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09578810500066498>
- Tauheed, T., & Ishtiaq, I. (2021). An Empirical Examination of Relative Income Hypothesis: Evidence from Pakistan. *Business & Economic Review*, 13(1), 1–18. <https://doi.org/10.22547/ber/13.1.1>